

Studies on the Composition and Stability Constants of Some Bivalent Metal Complexes of 2N-(3,5-Dinitro Salicylidene)-5-Phenyl-1,3,4 Thiadiazole Schiff Base

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Manuscript received 19 July 1981, revised 11 March 1983, accepted 1 September 1983

The composition, protonation constant of 2N-(3,5-dinitro salicylidene)-5-phenyl-1,3,4 thiadiazole and formation constants of its metal chelates with Cu(II), Hg(II) and Ni(II) in 50% ethanol-water system have been determined by Irving-Rossotti method at various ionic strengths at $25 \pm 1^\circ$. The order of stability of the metal chelates is Cu(II) > Hg(II) > Ni(II). Solid complexes were also separated. Chemical analyses suggest a 1 : 2 stoichiometry of metal : ligand.

NO complex of Cu(II), Hg(II) and Ni(I) ions has been reported with 2N-(3,5-dinitro salicylidene)-5-phenyl-1,3,4 thiadiazole Schiff base so far. This encouraged the present investigation.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of reagent grade. Standard solutions of copper sulphate, nickel sulphate and mercuric chloride were prepared in conductivity water and metal contents estimated by standard methods. The solution of 2N-(3,5-dinitro salicylidene)-5-phenyl-1,3,4 thiadiazole (DNSPT) was prepared in absolute alcohol.

Carbonate free NaOH solution used in potentiometric titrations was prepared in conductivity water. Stock solutions of sodium perchlorate (neutral) and perchloric acid were prepared in conductivity water.

An Elico pH meter, model Lt-10, having glass and saturated calomel electrodes was used for the titrations. The pH meter was calibrated with potassium hydrogen phthalate solution (pH 4.05). An Elico conductivity bridge, Model CM-80 (cell constant 1.09) was used for the determination of conductance of the complex.

Preparation of the ligand: The ligand 2N-(3,5-dinitro salicylidene)-5-phenyl-1,3,4 thiadiazole was prepared by refluxing equimolar quantities of 3,5-dinitro salicylaldehyde and 2-amino-5-phenyl-1,3,4 thiadiazole in absolute alcohol for 3 hr on a water bath. The product was repeatedly crystallised in alcohol to get an analytically pure compound, m.p. 217° . The compound was characterised by elemental analysis and infrared spectral studies. The ligand may be represented as shown below.

Preparation of the metal chelates: Metal complexes of the Schiff base were prepared by refluxing aqueous solution of the metal salt and alcoholic solution of the ligand in 1 : 2 molar ratio for 2 to 3 hr. The metal salts used were copper acetate, nickel acetate and mercuric chloride. The insoluble complexes that separated out on cooling were filtered, washed, dried in vacuum and analysed for the metal and nitrogen. The results are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA

Composition	Colour	Found Analysis % ; (Calcd.)	
		Metal	Nitrogen
(C ₁₅ H ₇ N ₃ OS) ₂ -Cu(II)	Green	9.40 (9.43)	20.73 (20.78)
(C ₁₅ H ₇ N ₃ OS) ₂ -Hg(II)	Buff	24.70 (24.74)	17.20 (17.27)
(C ₁₅ H ₇ N ₃ OS) ₂ -Ni(II)	Yellow green	8.71 (8.77)	20.82 (20.93)

Conductometric study: Jobs² method was employed to establish the composition of the complexes conductometrically.

Potentiometric study: Bjerrum-Calvin^{3,4} technique modified by Irving-Rossotti⁵ was employed for determining the stability constant of the metal complexes. For this purpose, the following three mixtures were prepared.

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- A. Perchloric acid 0.1 M.
- B. Perchloric acid 0.1 M + DNSPT 0.005 M.
- C. Perchloric acid 0.1 M + DNSPT 0.005 M + metal solution 0.001 M.

The concentration of the common ingredients were identical in the different mixtures. An appropriate amount of neutral sodium perchlorate (1M) was added to maintain the desired ionic strength. These mixtures were titrated against standard sodium hydroxide solution (0.1 M). Since pH titrations were carried out in 50% v/v ethanol-water medium, appropriate corrections in all pH meter readings were made as suggested by Van Uitert *et al*⁶.

A graph of pH versus the volume of alkali added was plotted. The three titration curves were referred as acid titration curve, ligand titration curve and complex titration curve.

Results and Discussion

Proton-ligand stability constants :

The values of $\bar{n}_H$ at various pH values were calculated from the acid titration curve and ligand titration curve using the formula of Irving and Rossotti. Calculation of proton-ligand stability constants was carried out by plotting a graph of $\bar{n}_H$ against pH, extended between 0.2 to 0.95 in the $\bar{n}_H$ scale. The pK_a values corresponding to $\bar{n}_H=0.5$ was obtained from the curve. However, the best values of pK_a of the ligand was found from the plot of $\log \bar{n}_H / (1-\bar{n}_H)$ vs pH. The plot was found to be a straight line with intercept equal to pK_a and slope equal to unity, suggesting that only one proton was dissociated. The values of proton-ligand stability constants obtained at various ionic strengths are given in Table 2.

Metal-ligand stability constant :

From the three titration curves, $\bar{n}$ values of the metal-complex were determined at various pH values. From these data the corresponding pL values were calculated. The $\bar{n}$ values were then plotted against the corresponding pL values to get the formation curves of the metal complex equilibria.

It is observed that the metal ligand curve is well separated from the ligand titration curves, suggesting thereby that the liberation of proton is due to chelation. The $\bar{n}$ values for each system were calculated until the pH of precipitation. Second buffer region starts after this pH, which explains the gradual consumption of hydrogen ion by metal in formation of metal hydroxide. The value of $\bar{n}$ obtained for Cu(II), Ni(II) and Hg(II) system was less than 2 before the onset of precipitation. This indicates the formation of MR^+ and MR_2 complex species in solution, where R is ligand. The value of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ for Cu(II), Ni(II) Hg(II) was obtained by direct observation of the formation curves ($\bar{n}=0.5$ and 1.5) as shown in Table 2. The values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were refined by computational methods⁷ viz. interpolation at various $\bar{n}$ method, mid point method and interpolation at half $\bar{n}$ values.

As the ionic strength increases the values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ decrease. This observation is in agreement with the Debye-Huckel⁸ equation. The observed order of stabilities for the above metal ions is Cu(II) > Hg(II) > Ni(II) and conforms to Irving Williams⁹ order of stability.

Conductometric study and chemical analyses of the metal chelates suggest a 1 : 2 stoichiometry

TABLE 2—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANT DATA ; TEMP. $-25 \pm 1^\circ$

A*	log KH ₁	$\mu = 0.05$			$\mu = 0.10$			$\mu = 0.15$			
		I*	II	III	I	II	III	I	II	III	
B	6.45				6.15				5.80		
	6.45				6.15				5.85		
<i>Metals</i>											
Cu(II)	log K ₁	6.14	6.10	6.15	5.40	5.59	5.79	4.75	4.74	4.89	
	log K ₂	5.10	5.10	5.07	5.05	5.24	4.93	4.40	4.39	4.45	
	log β_n	11.24	11.20	11.22	10.45	10.83	10.72	9.15	9.13	9.34	
	log K _{av}	5.62			5.22			4.57			
Hg(II)	log K ₁ /K ₂	1.04			0.35			0.35			
	log K ₁	5.00	4.93	5.09	5.05	5.25	5.20	4.12	4.12	4.31	
	log K ₂	4.45	4.38	4.37	4.35	4.55	4.28	3.72	3.72	3.59	
	log β_n	9.45	9.31	9.46	9.40	9.80	9.48	7.84	7.84	7.90	
Ni(II)	log K _{av}	4.72			4.70			3.92			
	log K ₁ /K ₂	0.55			0.70			0.40			
	log K ₁	4.46	4.50	4.56	3.90	4.01	4.26	4.10	4.17	4.33	
	log K ₂	3.85	3.82	3.87	3.55	3.66	3.29	3.25	3.32	3.19	
	log β_n	8.31	8.32	8.43	7.45	7.67	7.55	7.35	7.49	7.52	
	log K _{av}	4.15			3.72			3.67			
	log K ₁ /K ₂	0.61			0.35			0.85			

*A - Interpolation at half $\bar{n}_H$ values, B - Linear plot method, *I - Interpolation at half $\bar{n}$ values, II - Mid point method, III - Interpolation at various $\bar{n}$ values.

of metal : ligand. The probable structure of the complex may be written as.

References

1. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans Publication, London, 1961.
2. P. JOB, *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, 9, 113.
3. J. BJERRUM, "Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solution", Haase, Copenhagen, 1941, p. 298.
4. M. CALVIN and K. W. WILSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 2903.
5. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 2904.
6. L. G. VANUITERT and C. G. HAAS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 451.
7. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397.
8. S. NASANEN and EKMAN, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1952, 6, 1389.
9. H. M. IRVING and R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *Nature*, 1948, 162, 746.